

The impacts of real-time versus scheduled public transport service data when analysing patterns of accessibility

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Summary

Scheduled public transport data has been used extensively for estimating travel times in measuring accessibility to a wide range of services by alternative modes of transport. However, fewer studies to date have investigated the implications of using real-time travel data versus transit schedule data to investigate spatial patterns of accessibility. The overall aims of this study are to display the potential uses of live transit data that can be used to examine the accessibility differences introduced by using open data sources of real-time traffic data. Drawing on case studies for Cardiff and Swansea, the aim is to explore the implications of differences between scheduled and actual bus provision for accessibility to POIs in the respective cities. We conclude by suggesting that such impacts are often overlooked when using scheduled timetable data in accessibility analysis.

Keywords: Open-Source; Predictive Analysis; Real-time versus scheduled data; Accessibility Implications; Isochrones, SIRI-VM.

1. Introduction

Previous studies have explored the implications of using automated data collection systems and vehicle location data to examine different aspects of service reliability; Aemmer et al (2022) for example used bus network data for Seattle to develop an online visualization tool to examine the impacts of real-time data on a range of performance measures. Others have implemented web-GIS approaches to investigate the performance of real-time versus static General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) data for on-time and route speed calculations (Dardas et al., 2022). A more recent study has used space-time prism-based measures to examine the impact of short- and longer-term disruptions to the public transit system as evidenced by an analysis of GTFS Realtime (GTFS-RT) data (Liu et al., 2024). However, comparatively few studies have explored the impacts of using real-time data to examine variations in accessibility measures. The aim of this study is to investigate the potential of Service Interface for Real-time Information Vehicle Monitoring (SIRI-VM) data made available by the Department for Transport (DfT, 2020) to derive cumulative opportunity measures of accessibility based on actual not scheduled services.

Wessel et al. (2017) drew attention to the potential for using real-time vehicle location data to improve the accuracy of GTFS data to represent observed rather than scheduled transit services. Such data they suggest can be used to examine various elements of network performance, reliability and accessibility. Through an analysis of average accessibility to jobs in Toronto using scheduled and real-time ('retrospective') data for comparable periods, they found that "substantial aggregate accessibility differences exist between scheduled and observed services". They further suggest that "this 'error' in the scheduled GTFS data may have implications for many types of measurements commonly derived from GTFS data." Others have investigated the equity implications of travel time uncertainty using the example of transit-based accessibility to healthcare facilities in Columbus, Ohio (Lee and Kim, 2023). Their findings suggest that "traditional measures of accessibility that do not consider the impact of travel time uncertainty cannot accurately capture the social and racial inequity in healthcare

accessibility via transit (Lee and Kim, 2023; p. 1). There is a need for network analyses that include real-time information with which to monitor the impacts of such changes.

2. Research Aims and Objectives

Few studies have used such sources to differentiate the accessibility implications of real-time traffic data in UK cities. An exception is the work of Forth (2023) who conducted a study in Bristol and Leeds, matching every bus to its timetable and producing a version of the Great Britain bus timetable in GTFS format. This version reflected only the buses that ran, with recorded positions updated every minute. The GTFS files were then loaded into Open Trip Planner 2.2, where the Isochrone feature was used to calculate the reachable area based on both real bus movements and timetabled data. Building on this work, the aim of this research is to analyse differences in bus access between published timetable GTFS and GTFS constructed from live SIRI-VM data. This analysis will not only examine changes in accessible areas but also assess potential impacts on access to key services, such as healthcare facilities, hospitals, and supermarkets. Understanding these differences is crucial, as most accessibility analyses rely on operator-published GTFS, which do not account for daily fluctuations in bus routes. Consequently, these analyses may misrepresent real-world access, underscoring the need for more accurate methods.

3. Methods/Datasets

Figure 1 illustrates the methodology used to process SIRI-VM data into usable GTFS information, which can then be fed into a routing engine to generate accessibility and trip data for further analysis. As shown in Figure 1, the SIRI journey reference is matched to the journey codes, allowing the real-time trip data to be aligned with new files. This process generates a refined GTFS dataset, which can then be used to scrutinize the original timetable published monthly. Preliminary research has drawn on data for the cities of Cardiff and Swansea to investigate the implications of using real-time data versus scheduled timetable data (using in the first instance, cumulative accessibility measures).

The study draws on a data source that provides real-time data from the Bus Open Data Service (BODS); this service is hosted and maintained by the UK government and provides users with the ability to download converted TransXchange GTFS timetables, GTFS-RT and vehicle location data with SIRI-VM (DfT, 2025). In addition to the acquisition of timetable data, the research also relies on Points of Interest (POI) data to conduct the accessibility analysis. Since the application is designed to be open-source the data supplied to the system also remains open-source and free to access. The supply of POI data for example is accessed from the Consumer Data Research Centre (Consumer Data Research Centre, 2025). Finally, the road network that is paired with GTFS to make the graph for the routing engine calculations is sourced from OpenStreetMap (Geofabrik, 2025). This data helps the routing engine understand the roads that are walkable after a bus user exits the bus.

Figure 1: Workflow to build GTFS from SIRI data

4. Accessibility impacts of real versus scheduled times

To demonstrate the impact of cancelled routes on accessibility, the approach taken has been to compare changes in access scores and isochrone shapes when using real-time bus data versus timetable-based data. By highlighting these differences, this section will provide valuable insight into the potential inaccuracies inherent in timetable-based analyses. It will underscore the importance of considering real-world access scores when evaluating and drawing conclusions about bus accessibility. All calculations will be from traffic hubs in the centre of Cardiff and Swansea using a 60-minute catchment area from the same time (8.30 am). The following images will display two isochrones with base GTFS being blue and either GTFS-RT or SIRI-VM being red on the map.

The first example highlights changes in accessibility within Cardiff, revealing notable differences when compared to the monthly submitted timetable data. As shown in Figure 2, a scheduled trip in the southern part of Cardiff did not occur, resulting in a reduction in accessibility for that area. The graph in Figure 2 illustrates the impact of missing services on local residents' access to key destinations. For example, while TransXchange data suggests that 55 gyms are accessible within 60 minutes, real-world access derived from SIRI data reports only 50. This discrepancy underscores the often-overlooked inaccuracy of timetable-based analyses, as many studies rely solely on published schedules when assessing bus accessibility.

Figure 2: Comparisons in access between TransXchange and SIRI-VM data within Cardiff (Generated from city centre hub: Thursday 8.30 am, 60-minute catchment)

The second example examines accessibility changes in Swansea, Wales' second-largest city. Figure 3 compares accessibility derived from the submitted timetable data with that based on SIRI-generated information. As with the Cardiff example, the maps reveal significant differences between the two datasets. However, in Swansea, all accessibility changes stem from trips that either failed to arrive or were cancelled. This further demonstrates that analyses based solely on timetable data may misrepresent real-world accessibility conditions.

Figure 3: Comparisons in access between TransXchange and SIRI-VM within Swansea (Generated from city centre hub: Thursday 8.30am, 60-minute catchment)

Overall, these examples highlight the critical disparities between measures of accessibility based on scheduled timetable data and actual accessibility based on real-time service performance. These discrepancies emphasize the limitations of timetable-based assessments and provide valuable insights into the reliability of public transport services across different regions. Incorporating both scheduled (potential) and real-time (actual) accessibility data could enable researchers and transport agencies to refine their analyses, potentially leading to a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of public transport accessibility.

5. Preliminary Conclusions/Future Research

Future research could significantly benefit from incorporating real-time data, such as live traffic conditions, service delays, and passenger load information. By leveraging these dynamic inputs, accessibility analyses could move beyond static assumptions to reflect real-world, real-time conditions. This shift would provide transport planners and policymakers with up-to-date insights into current transit conditions, allowing for more informed decision-making. Real-time data integration would also enhance the accuracy of accessibility predictions, particularly in rapidly changing scenarios, such as weather-related disruptions or peak travel periods. Such advancements would support timely interventions to optimize transport services and improve user experiences.

While there has been recent research on the impact of congestion on accessibility to opportunities and jobs that account for congestion-adjusted operating speeds in car-centric cities (Acharya et al., 2025), less research has focused on the implications of changes to public transport timetables on accessibility.

The availability of online, open data sources of actual vehicle locations offers the potential to track the provision of bus services and investigate their impacts on access to a wider range of services based on performance rather than scheduled services (Nalin et al., 2025). The approach taken in the current study highlights the potential of using real-time travel information instead of scheduled GTFS data to more accurately represent accessibility to services and opportunities.

Ongoing research presented at the conference will demonstrate the variability of isochrones for different days of the week that illustrates variations during the day (and the potential to include opening times of POIs in accessibility measures). This can be extended to examine such implications with a wider range of accessibility measures (such as the Floating Catchment Area (FCA) scores) and for an extended list of services/facilities using actual service conditions. Such research will include an analysis of the implications for the social equity of provision by comparing spatial variations in scheduled versus real-time services. This will also explore the potential of using GTFS-RT data, which holds promise for generating live statistics on delays and trip alterations. Unlike SIRI-VM, which tracks vehicle locations, GTFS-RT provides data on delays and changes to bus arrival and departure times. This offers a more realistic and dynamic view of accessibility compared to timetable-based data. When combined with SIRI-VM data, this analysis could deliver accurate insights into the inaccuracies of timetable data. Moreover, it could equip researchers and public transport institutions with unique tools and methodologies to enhance future accessibility analyses and improve decision-making in public transport planning.

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Biographies

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